

Letter of Presentation

This certifies that **Theo Tsenis** attended the 18th International Conference on Climate Change: Impacts & Responses at Dimokratias 1, Rodos 851 00, Greece between 20-22 April 2026.

Theo Tsenis presented the paper titled:

Hybrid Ground–Aerial Forest Inventory Using Quadraped Lidar DBH Ground Truth for Allometric Calibration of Drone-Based Crown Measurements

The annual conference is an integral component of the Climate Change: Impacts & Responses Research Network. Founded in 2009, the Climate Change: Impacts & Responses Research Network is brought together by a common concern for the science of, and social responses to, climate change.

We thank you for your valuable contribution. The annual conference is an integral component of the Climate Change: Impacts & Responses Research Network.

Regards,

Dr. Phillip Kalantzis Cope
Chief Social Scientist
Common Ground Research Networks